

Analysis of Customer Retention through Dimensions of Service Quality, Product Quality, and Customer Satisfaction Using Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) at 3 Fast Food Restaurants in Surabaya

(Case Study: Carl's Jr., Burger King, and McDonald's)

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Abstract: The shift in perception of the community that eating at fast food restaurants is more prestigious than eating at home has become the most common reason why fast food restaurants are more preferred by Indonesians. This research was conducted to determine the most influencing factors on customer retention of fast food restaurants in Surabaya and to determine which fast food restaurants that have the highest customer retention. The population is the citizen of Surabaya who are visiting fast food restaurants including Carl's Jr., Burger King and McDonald's with a sample size of 150 people which determined based on purposive sampling techniques. As the results are tangible (physical evidence) is the most influential factor on customer retention of fast food restaurants in Surabaya and Burger King customers have the highest customer retention rates than the customer retention from Carl's Jr., and McDonald's. The main recommendations given to the management of the fast food restaurant, especially Burger King, Carl's Jr. and McDonald's is to improve service quality (tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy), product quality (food), and customer satisfaction in order to increase the customer retention rate of fast food restaurants in Surabaya.

Keywords: *Customer Retention, Customer Satisfaction, Product Quality, Service Quality*

I. INTRODUCTION

Fast food restaurants are one of the most popular types of restaurants in Indonesian society. The shift in perception in the community that eating at fast food restaurants is more prestigious than eating at home has become the most common reason why fast food restaurants are in great demand by Indonesians. The impact of this phenomenon is the mushrooming of restaurants offering fast food, or increasing menu choices. Roy Morgan's survey results (2018) have found that customer retention in fast food restaurants in Indonesia is indeed high, where there are around 55 million Indonesians (34.3%) visit fast food restaurants in an average of 6 months. Fast food restaurants are restaurants that can supply food quickly and require minimum service which is usually a chain of franchise restaurants (Siew et al., 2016). Fast food restaurants are restaurants that can supply food quickly and require minimum service which is usually a chain of franchise restaurants (Siew et al., 2016). Food quality has a major influence on customer satisfaction, so it is one of the most important factors that results in higher levels of customer satisfaction and high customer retention (Al Tit, 2015). Customer retention in fast food restaurants is also influenced by the level of customer satisfaction in related restaurants. Customer satisfaction is the extent to which a product's perceived performance matches customer expectations. Based on overall customer satisfaction, the results of research Siew et al., (2016) showed that McDonald's is the most fast food restaurant that satisfies its customers, then followed by KFC, Pizza Hut, Wing Zone and Domino Pizza. Different findings related to customer retention of fast food restaurants in the world (Al-Tit, 2015; Goceri & Goceri, 2017; Kecek and Gürdal, 2016; Siew et al., 2016) then encouraged researchers to conduct similar research in Indonesia, especially in Indonesia, Surabaya city. Some fast food restaurants that will be examined in this study are Carl's Jr., Burger King and McDonald's.

Carl's Jr. is one of the famous burger brands from the United States that started its business in 1941, which is a hot dog in a suburb in Los Angeles. Currently Carl's Jr. spread over 39 countries and 20 of its outlets are located in Indonesia, spread across Jakarta, Bogor, Bekasi, Bandung and Surabaya. One of Carl's Jr. outlets in the Surabaya region located on Jl. Raya Darmo No. 12, Surabaya. The interesting thing about Carl's Jr. products. is that the meat of Carls Jr. 100% authentic and not mixed with flour or other ingredients. In addition, customers can also choose the composition of the burger filling. Other fast food restaurants that also have a big name in Indonesia, especially in the city of Surabaya, namely Burger King. Burger King first appeared in Indonesia in the 1980s and was closed in 1998 after being affected by the monetary crisis then in April 2007, Burger King returned to Indonesia. They one of the outlets located on Jalan Jemursari No. 260, Surabaya. When viewed from the traffic of visitors, Burger King Jemursari Surabaya is almost never empty of visitors. That is because there are many promos that are offered every day. The preliminary survey results show that this August, Burger King offers a "August Coupon" promo that gives a discount of 10-50% for some burger packages, such as the Spicy Steakhouse Package, Moza Rasher Deluxe, and BBQ Rasher Tender crisp. Another fast food restaurant which is the object of this research is McDonald's. This restaurant has been present in Indonesia since 1991, with the development of products based on chicken meat. Most of McDonald's customers come mostly to eat burgers and various types of wrap and ice cream. Another advantage of McDonald's that is considered important by customers is the price that tends to be cheaper than its competitors such as Burger King or Carl's Jr. At present, McDonald's has around 36,000 outlets worldwide. McDonald's outlets located on Jl. Basuki Rahmat No.21-23, Embong Kaliasin, Kec. Genteng, SBY City, is one of the outlets with the most visitors, especially in the afternoon until the evening. The survey results of the researchers also found that many customers admitted that they had made McDonald's Basra (red. Basuki Rahmat) as a regular gathering or hangout location.

The results of the initial survey of researchers also found that each of the 10 people from the three restaurants claimed to have different consumption experiences in the three restaurants. Carl's Jr. customer claimed to have consumed products at the restaurant at least 2 times a week, then 60% of them claimed to move to Burger King or McDonald's when there was a certain promotion, while the remaining 40% still chose Carl's Jr. as his favorite fast food restaurant. Burger King customers claim to have consumed products at the restaurant at least 2-3 times a week, then 20% of them claimed to move to Carl's Jr. and 30% prefer McDonald's for wider space reasons, while the remaining 50% still choose Burger King as their favorite fast food restaurant given the daily promos for certain products. In contrast to Carls Jr. and Burger King, McDonald's customers claim to have consumed products at the restaurant at least 3 times a week, then 30% of them claimed to move to Burger King or Carl's Jr. for reasons of friend / relative requests, while the remaining 70% still choose McDonald's as their favorite fast food restaurant because they think McDonald's products taste better than Carl's Jr. or Burger King.

In this study, customer retention will be analyzed using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) approach. The AHP model has been applied in the selection of fast food restaurants in various countries. However, the AHP model has not been actively studied in Indonesia. Therefore, this study aims to fill the research gap by studying the selection of fast food restaurants in Surabaya with the AHP model. As the results of the study of Marinkovic et al. (2015) have explained that the AHP model can be used effectively to evaluate significant ranking factors by customers in choosing a restaurant, so it has the capacity to include and realistically reflect the decision maker preference structure that has been confirmed in practice through various AHP applications, because AHP also take into account the interaction of the elements of decision making.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS

II.1 Customer Retention

The current business condition is described by intense competition, so customer retention is seen as one of the success factors of the company's sustainability. Until now, there have been many definitions given by experts regarding customer retention. Customer retention can be defined as the activity of converting new customers into regular customers by providing excellent customer service so as to increase long-term customer satisfaction (Kotler and Armstrong, 2015). Customer retention is a form of loyalty related to loyal behavior measured by customer buying behavior as indicated by the high frequency of customers making product purchases (Mandal, 2016). In other words, customer retention is the result of the customer's attitude or behavior towards the service performance that he consumes, so there is an interest in repurchase as a customer's desire to buy or return to the same organization in the long run (Sari et al., 2018). Customer retention can be interpreted as customer immunity to all temptations from competing companies through various marketing tools to move into customers in the company. This immunity arises from the presence of happy feelings from customers towards the company's products or services after comparing the performance of the company's products or services with competitors' products or services (Anggraini et al., 2016). Customers who have high retention will not mind paying a slightly higher price, in contrast to new customers who are

waiting for discounts from the company. This happens because customers who have high retention believe that a slightly higher price indicates higher quality. These customers usually shop throughout the year, even after discount periods at the stores of their choice and find it appropriate to carry out these shopping activities because they do not care too much about the value of the money component (Ang and Buttle, 2016).

II.2 Service Quality

Service quality means the overall assessment carried out by customers on the superiority of service offerings which is influenced by the company's ability to meet customer needs according to their level of expectation (Sharma, 2017). Service quality means the overall assessment carried out by customers on the superiority of service offerings which is influenced by the company's ability to meet customer needs according to their level of expectation (Sharma, 2017). For example, a fast food restaurant can give a very low value of money when perceived quality is below expectations at the price charged, while dining restaurants can provide high value for money when perceived quality exceeds expectations at the price charged (Bowie & Buttle, 2013). One of the model that can be used to measure service quality is to use the SERVQUAL model, which is based on the assumption that customers compare service performance on relevant dimensions with ideal / perfect standards for each service dimension (Sharma, 2017). These dimensions are tangible, such as equipment, personnel appearance and physical facilities; responsiveness, such as willingness to help and provide fast service; reliability, such as the ability to perform promised service reliably; assurance, such as the knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to inspire trust and trust; and empathy, such as the individual attention the company gives to its customers (El-Saghier, 2015). According to Zeithmal et al. (2011) the five dimensions of service quality can be applied to various service contexts, namely: Tangible (physical evidence) is the appearance of physical facilities, equipment, employee performance and communication materials provided by the company to support the services provided to customers; Reliability is the ability to provide the promised service accurately and reliably; Responsiveness is a willingness to help customers and provide services quickly; Assurance is the knowledge, courtesy and ability of the company and its employees to foster trust and confidence in customers; Empathy is the care and individual attention that a company provides to customers. The essence of empathy is to deliver a personal or customized service, with the consideration that each customer is someone unique and must be treated specifically.

II.3 Product Quality

Product quality is the customer's perception of the overall quality or excellence of a product or service, with respect to the intended purpose, relative to an alternative (Ehsan & Ehsani, 2015). Product quality means the overall features and characteristics of the product produced by the product's ability to satisfy the stated or implied customer needs (Kotler & Armstrong, 2015). In other words, the term product quality is believed to be a collection of the overall characteristics and features of available products that are made based on their ability to meet all the needs and requests given, both the safety criteria, appearance and dietary acceptance (Phan & Nguyen, 2016). Related to food and beverage products, product quality can be interpreted as a customer evaluation of the suitability of food products from a restaurant or restaurant. Product quality also means product compatibility with its presentation. For example, the perception of the quality of boiled egg products, toast, cereals and juices may be more interesting when served at breakfast, but the same food will be considered very bad if served at dinner (Mohaydin et al., 2017). Food quality is the most important criterion in the overall evaluation of customers of a restaurant and shows an important element that must be provided by the restaurant to meet customer needs and satisfaction. General characteristics of food quality emphasize that quality consists of several elements, such as: food presentation, taste, diversity of choices, healthy choices, freshness, and temperature (Hanaysha, 2016).

II.4 Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is the extent to which a product's perceived performance matches customer expectations. If product performance falls short of expectations, the customer is not satisfied. If performance is as expected, the customer is satisfied. If performance exceeds expectations, the customer is very satisfied (Kotler & Armstrong, 2015). In other words, satisfaction is the feeling of pleasure or disappointment of a customer resulting from comparing the performance (or results) of a product that is felt with expectations (Razak et al., 2016). Customers have predicted the level of service in their minds before the service was received. This prediction level is the result of a search and selection process, when the customer decides to buy a service. During the service, the customer feels the service performance and compares it with the predicted service level. An assessment of satisfaction is then formed based on this comparison. In short, customers evaluate service performance by comparing what they expect with what they receive from the company (Loveloek & Wirtz, 2016). Customer satisfaction is very important for the success of the restaurant business. Some restaurants will survive if they consistently provide a satisfying experience.

II.5 Research Framework

The model in this study can be described as follows. Based on the research model, the factors assumed to influence customer retention in this study are customer retention, service quality (including: tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy), product quality (food), customer satisfaction and customer retention of three fast food restaurants operating in Surabaya, namely Carl's Jr., Burger King and McDonald's.

Figure 1. Research Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is a quantitative research and data used in this study were obtained from primary sources which is collected by distributing questionnaires to 150 respondents who are visiting fast food restaurants which are Carl's Jr., Burger King and McDonald's with the characteristics of male and female respondents aged 17 - 60 years old, live in Surabaya, and have visited and bought food at the three fast food restaurants which are Carl's Jr., Burger King, and McDonald's at least 2 times in the last 6 months. The scale used in the questionnaire is a ratio scale through a pairwise matrix, where there is no perception of research respondents with a value of 0 (zero) and negative numbers, but using a scale of 1-9 to be able to qualify, because the smallest element is 1/9 and the largest is 9 (Kuncoro, 2014). A scale adapted from Saaty is shown below.

Table 3.1. Scale of Analytical Hierarchy Process

Score	Definition
1	Equally important
3	Somewhat more important
5	Much more important
7	Very much more important
9	Absolutely more important
2, 4, 6, 8	Intermediate values

Source: Data Processed, 2019.

Data analysis method used in this study is the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). AHP is a decision making method developed to prioritize alternatives when several criteria must be considered, and allow decision making to arrange complex problems into a hierarchical form or integrated set of levels.

The steps of the AHP method according to Rahmayanti (2010) are as follows:

1. Compilation of the problem hierarchy structure
2. Priority Determination
3. Consistency
4. Priority Synthesis

5. Analytical Hierarchy Process axioms
6. Multi Participant Comparative Assessment

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of normalization weight priority from the questionnaire filled out by all research respondents can be displayed as in Table 4.1 below. The priority ranking of the factors that influence customer retention of fast food restaurant in Surabaya is: (1) Display of physical facilities, equipment, employee appearance and communication materials provided by the company to support services provided to customers (tangible) is ranked first which influence the retention of fast food restaurant customers in Surabaya; (2) The ability of employees to provide promised services accurately and reliably (reliability) is ranked second which influence the retention of fast food restaurant customers in Surabaya; (3) The willingness of employees to help customers and provide services quickly (responsiveness), as well as the knowledge, courtesy and ability of the company and its employees to foster trust and confidence in customers

Table 4.1 Normalization and Priority Weight Matrix 7x7

	<i>Tangible</i>	<i>Reliability</i>	<i>Responsive</i>	<i>Assurance</i>	<i>Empathy</i>	<i>Quality</i>	<i>Satisfaction</i>	<i>Total Weight</i>	<i>Eigen Vector</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>CR</i>
<i>Tangible</i>	0,2500	0,1935	0,3000	0,3000	0,2500	0,2353	0,2353	1,7641	0,2520	0,01	0,009
<i>Reliability</i>	0,2500	0,1935	0,1500	0,1500	0,2500	0,1765	0,1765	1,3465	0,1924		
<i>Responsive</i>	0,1250	0,1935	0,1500	0,1500	0,1250	0,1765	0,1765	1,0965	0,1566		
<i>Assurance</i>	0,1250	0,1935	0,1500	0,1500	0,1250	0,1765	0,1765	1,0965	0,1566		
<i>Empathy</i>	0,1250	0,0968	0,1500	0,1500	0,1250	0,1176	0,1176	0,8821	0,1260		
<i>Quality</i>	0,0625	0,0645	0,0500	0,0500	0,0625	0,0588	0,0588	0,4072	0,0582		
<i>Satisfaction</i>	0,0625	0,0645	0,0500	0,0500	0,0625	0,0588	0,0588	0,4072	0,0582		
Total	1,0000	1,0000	1,0000	1,0000	1,0000	1,0000	1,0000	7,0000	1,0000		

Source: Data Processed, 2019.

(assurance), ranks third which influence customer retention of fast food restaurants in Surabaya; (4) Concern and individual attention provided by the company to the customer, understanding what the customer wants, willing to listen to whatever is complained of by the customer, and responding to various complaints expressed by the customer well are ranked fourth which influence customer retention of fast food restaurants in Surabaya; and (5) The overall features and characteristics of the product produced by the product's ability to satisfy the stated or implied needs of the product (product quality) and the extent to which the perceived performance of a product matches customer expectations, is ranked fourth which influence customer retention fast food restaurant in Surabaya.

Table 4.2 Weight Priority of Tangible

	Carl's Jr.	Burger King	McDonald's	Eigen Vector	CI	CR
Carl's Jr.	0,3333	0,4286	0,2000	0,3206	0,07	0,1
Burger King	0,3333	0,4286	0,6000	0,4540		
McDonald's	0,3333	0,1429	0,2000	0,2254		

Source: Data Processed, 2019.

Burger King is considered to have the appearance of physical facilities, equipment, employee appearance and communication materials provided by the company to support the services provided to customers (tangible) that are better than Carl's Jr. and McDonald's. Burger King has better equipment in the restaurant, where the tables and chairs used are made of higher quality wood compared to plastic and iron also have a strong enough durability, they are very concerned about the cleanliness of toilet facilities, and also chose to provide warm ambience, if we pay attention from the perspective of room lighting, Burger King is more yellowish, while McDonald's chooses white ambience, and Carl's Jr. has dimmer or dim lighting.

Table 4.3 Weight Priority of Reliability

	Carl's Jr.	Burger King	McDonald's	Eigen Vector	CI	CR
Carl's Jr.	0,4000	0,4000	0,4000	0,4000		
Burger King	0,4000	0,4000	0,4000	0,4000	0	0
McDonald's	0,2000	0,2000	0,2000	0,2000		

Source: Data Processed, 2019.

Burger King and Carl's Jr. are considered to have employees with the ability to provide the promised services accurately and reliably (reliability) which is better (superior) than McDonald's. Both of them managed to provide training for their employees with the aim of training its employees in providing services to consumers, this is also influenced by employee performance which must be adjusted to customer expectations in terms of timeliness. In addition, the same service for all customers, a high degree of sympathy and accuracy so that mistakes do not occur. Thus, the accuracy, speed, friendliness and comfort provided by fast food restaurant employees to customers is the second key to customer retention based on the results of this study.

Table 4.4 Weight Priority of Reponsiveness

	Carl's Jr.	Burger King	McDonald's	Eigen Vector	CI	CR
Carl's Jr.	0,3333	0,4000	0,2500	0,3278		
Burger King	0,3333	0,4000	0,5000	0,4111	0,03	0,05
McDonald's	0,3333	0,2000	0,2500	0,2611		

Source: Data Processed, 2019.

Burger King is considered to have employees with a willingness to help customers and provide a better services than Carl's Jr. and McDonald's. It can be seen from the attitude of every employee in Burger King when serving customers, where they look more skillful but still gentle and polite in serving and do not give or show the impression of being rushed or like being chased. It shows that the awareness, desire and self-control of Burger King employees in helping customers and providing services quickly is very important in the quality of fast food restaurant services.

Table 4.5 Weight Priority of Assurance

	Carl's Jr	Burger King	McDonald's	Eigen Vector	CI	CR
Carl's Jr	0,3333	0,4000	0,2500	0,3278		
Burger King	0,3333	0,4000	0,5000	0,4111	0,03	0,05
McDonald's	0,3333	0,2000	0,2500	0,2611		

Source: Data Processed, 2019.

Burger King is considered to have employees with the knowledge, courtesy and ability of the company and its employees to foster trust and confidence in customers (assurance) better (superior) than Carl's Jr. and McDonald's. The results of this study indicate that assurance (certainty of service delivery) that is knowledge, courtesy, and the ability of employees to generate confidence and trust for customers is the third key in fast food restaurant customer retention. It can be seen from the way employees at Burger King when greeting new guests who have arrived and will make an order, they welcome them with a smile full of warmth to make consumers more confident to make transactions at Burger King, and if the desired menu runs out, they can choose words and facial expressions that make consumers feel comfortable to buy other available menus, little things like this that are often considered trivial instead give considerable impact on consumers.

Table 4.6 Weight Priority of Empathy

	Carl's Jr	Burger King	McDonald's	Eigen Vector	CI	CR
Carl's Jr	0,4000	0,4000	0,4000	0,4000		
Burger King	0,4000	0,4000	0,4000	0,4000	0	0
McDonald's	0,2000	0,2000	0,2000	0,2000		

Source: Data Processed, 2019.

Burger King and Carl's Jr. are considered to have employees with individual care and attention provided by the company to customers (empathy) who are better (superior) than McDonald's. The results of this study indicate that Burger King and Carl's employees have better understanding in what customers want, want to listen to whatever is complained by customers, and respond to various complaints expressed by customers well. It can be seen from the way Burger King and Carl's Jr employees respond to each complaint by providing a suggestion box so that there is a place to collect feedback given from each customer, in addition they receive every complaint and make the complaint as an ingredient to make improvements. This shows the seriousness of Burger King and Carl's Jr. in serving consumers with care and attention.

Table 4.7 Weight Priority of Product Quality

	Carl's Jr	Burger King	McDonald's	Eigen Vector	CI	CR
Carl's Jr	0,3333	0,4000	0,2500	0,3278		
Burger King	0,3333	0,4000	0,5000	0,4111	0,03	0,05
McDonald's	0,3333	0,2000	0,2500	0,2611		

Source: Data Processed, 2019.

The overall features and characteristics of the product that are produced by the product's ability to satisfy the stated or implied customer needs (product quality) from Burger King are considered better (superior) than Carl's Jr. and McDonald's. This shows that customers consider the quality of products owned by Burger King higher than those of Carl's Jr. and McDonald's. The quality of the product in question is closely related to the taste of the product, variety and innovation of the product, the level of hygiene, suitable portions, attractive packaging, the presence of halal guarantees, good aroma and the right price, but also can be seen Burger King provides beef (meat) which is more varied, and the bread they use has a softer texture than the bread used by Carls Jr. and McDonald's.

Table 4.8 Weight Priority of Customer Satisfaction

	Carl's Jr	Burger King	McDonald's	Eigen Vector	CI	CR
Carl's Jr	0,3333	0,4000	0,2500	0,3278		
Burger King	0,3333	0,4000	0,5000	0,4111	0,03	0
McDonald's	0,3333	0,2000	0,2500	0,2611		

Source: Data Processed, 2019.

The extent to which the perceived performance of a product is in line with customer expectations (customer satisfaction) from Burger King is considered higher (superior) than Carl's Jr. and McDonald's. This shows that the experience of customers in consuming fast food products from the three restaurants studied has led to a more positive customer perception of Burger King compared to Carl's Jr. and McDonald's. It can be seen from the form of satisfaction felt by consumers such as wanting to linger in a Burger King outlet, make repeated visits, and have a fixed preference for a type of product that is on the menu list, this is enough to show directly that consumers are satisfied with the performance and products provided at Burger King, or in other words in accordance with the expectations or expectations of customers when intending to make a visit at Burger King. In connection with the feeling of pleasure felt, the ability of fast food restaurants to meet customer expectations, employee confidence that eating at fast food restaurants can provide a satisfying experience, and overall, has pleased customers when eating at the restaurant.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) analysis, it has been found that tangibility (physical evidence) is the factor that most influences customer retention of fast food restaurants in Surabaya, and Burger King customers have higher customer retention rates than customer retention from Carl's and McDonald's.

Table 5.1 Managerial Implications

Current Research	Managerial Implications
Tangible (physical evidence) is the main factor that most influences customer retention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing complete facilities and a comfortable restaurant atmosphere. • Pay more attention to the maintenance of facilities owned. • Improving restaurant cleanliness.
Reliability is the second factor that influences customer retention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give awards to employees who are considered to work well. • Conduct training for employees so that they do not forget the services that should be provided to customers.
Responsiveness is the third factor that influences customer retention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasis on attention and accuracy when dealing with customer requests, questions and complaints. • Have employees who can quickly and responsibly provide services, take responsibility if something goes wrong in the selection of food menus, or help customers who are hesitate in placing an order. • Provide training to employees related to each service provided.
Assurance is the fourth factor that influences customer retention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employees must have good knowledge about all the product. • Employees must always speak politely to customers. • Employees must be able to maintain a safe feeling of customers when making payments.
Empathy is the fifth factor that influences customer retention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Place the manager as a central activity to motivate employees and participate actively in serving customer complaints. • Increase the active participation of managers in the service process. • Encourage managers to direct employees who are directly involved with customers.
Product quality is the sixth factor that influences customer retention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve product hygiene and adjust the portions • To avoid customers getting bored with their products, fast food restaurant management needs to create innovative new menus.
Customer satisfaction is the least factor that influences customer retention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continue to increase customer satisfaction. • Improve the overall quality.

Based on the results of this study, the main recommendations made by the management of fast food restaurant Burger King, Carl's Jr. and McDonald's is to improve service quality (tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy), product quality (food), and customer satisfaction in increasing customer retention of fast food restaurants in Surabaya. As for the suggestions that can be delivered based on the results of this study are as follows:

1. This study only uses three objects of fast food restaurants in Surabaya, so that further research is expected to be able to use more samples from different fast food restaurants to get the results of the study can be generalized related to the factors that influence the retention of fast food restaurant customers in Surabaya.
2. Future studies are expected to be able to complete the variables that already exist in this study, so as to further enhance understanding of the factors that influence customer retention of fast food restaurants in Surabaya, in addition to dimensions of service quality, product quality and customer satisfaction.

3. There are a lot of fast food restaurants in Surabaya, besides Carl's Jr., Burger King, and McDonald's. Therefore, future research can use a broader research object, so that the research can provide a broader picture of the factors that influence the retention of fast food restaurant customers in Surabaya.
4. The current research uses the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) approach to explain the results of the study, so that future research can use other data analysis techniques, for example: path analysis or structure equation model (SEM) to determine the effect of service quality, product quality and customer satisfaction on fast food restaurant customer retention in Surabaya.

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